

METHODOLOGICAL CONDITIONS OF STUDYING THE MANAGEMENT CULTURE OF EXECUTIVE STAFF

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Abstract. *The article highlights the personality of the leader, his important role in the field of management. The study of the management culture of the Executive Officer as well as the functional aspects of management are also revealed.*

Keywords: *executive staff, form of government, modern education, law, phenomenon, social organizations.*

Today, for the management of the educational system, the tasks of improvement are set based on the development of the functional tasks of management, the theoretical foundations and scientific-methodical support of the management process, and the monitoring of the innovative development of education. The development of a general educational institution largely depends on the skills of the leader in setting strategic and tactical goals and managing the process of achieving them.

Since the first days of independence in Uzbekistan, special attention has been paid to improving the quality of continuous education, its normative-legal and material-technical base has been fundamentally updated, and systematic work has been organized to train and improve the skills of leading personnel. Management of the general education system is evaluated as an independent direction of the personnel training system, including a clear limitation of the powers of management bodies at all levels of the continuous education system. In addition to the results achieved in this activity, it is necessary to purposefully organize research on the improvement of mechanisms for training highly qualified leaders in the general education system.

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" adopted on September 23, 2020, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 15, 2017 "On Approval of the Regulation on General Secondary Education" dated September 17, 2021 "On measures to improve the procedure for certification of pedagogic personnel of preschool, general secondary, special secondary, professional and extracurricular educational organizations", dated September 3, 2022. This dissertation research serves to a certain extent in the implementation of the tasks defined in the decision of October "On approving the concept of increasing the effectiveness of spiritual-educational and educational work in general secondary educational institutions" and other regulatory legal documents related to this issue.

The role of management in the development of man and society is unquestionable. Let us consider the phenomenon of governance in the human category.

Management is a specific manifestation of the mind, will and aspirations of people, expressed in the creation of a relevant social institution - a systematically organized set of human knowledge, behavior, social practice and activity. Management as a type of social practice has existed since the need for joint and purposeful activities of people.

Awareness of the phenomenon of social governance began with the recognition of the institution of power, or rather, divine power. Then other forms of social management began to appear and become aware. If earlier a person obeyed only his instincts, over time he was influenced by a more and more controlling force, that is, subjecting more and more people to general rules of behavior (control) was possible. This possibility has become a reality due to the formation of increasingly complex social management mechanisms.

People work together, so their activities are public and need to be managed. Any joint work done on a relatively large scale is managed. The nature of social governance has become increasingly complex. The mechanism of governing a primitive community consisting of an elder, a leader, a council, and some other institutions is much simpler than the mechanism of governing a modern society. The structure and functions of the modern state cannot be compared in complexity with the management mechanisms of primitive tribes.

Thus, we can say that social evolution accompanied by the complexity of social organizations and the increase in their size is related to the complexity of social management. The history of the development of society is the process of the complexity of the structure of the organization and the activities of people. The form of implementation of such a movement is the distribution of new types of activities and their isolation as a result of the development of the social division of labor along with the increase in the production force. The entire history of society has been subordinated to the goals of individual survival and social community.

In the history of mankind, management has faced radical changes several times. Management practice has undergone significant changes in its development. Sometimes management has changed so fundamentally that management revolutions have occurred when the transition from one qualitative state of management to another was made. All management revolutions are examples of separation and isolation of new activities.

The first of these is usually associated with the Sumerian and Egyptian civilizations, where the priestly caste became a caste of religious officials - leaders. Over time, in addition to observing religious rituals, priests began to deal with tax collection, state treasury management, and property affairs. Gradually, the clergy began to control vast properties and valuables, which required the systematic implementation of accounting, control, distribution and exchange functions.

For example, the art of management, the ability to plan and organize long-term work, and the effective use of material and human resources were clearly demonstrated during the construction of ancient Egyptian structures. As a result, there was a certain division of administration and its transformation into a means of commercial and religious activity. At the same stage, the corresponding type of life support (hunting, fishing, fruit gathering) is disappearing, and a radically new type of food supply - the organization of their production (agriculture, animal husbandry)) transition is taking place and this is giving impetus to the development of economic management.

Thus, as a result of the first management revolution, sometimes called religious-commercial, management was formed as a means of commercial and religious activity, and later became a social institution and professional profession.

The distinctive feature of the management culture of a modern leader is primarily formed under the influence of social mechanisms and is manifested as a driving force of social development. Therefore, one of the most important issues today is the formation of a highly

qualified management apparatus, the training of educated, qualified, modern-technological personnel who will become leaders of the state and society.

For centuries and thousands of years, humanity has entered a qualitatively new period of its development. When solving any problems, more and more we have to consider the "outer limits" of our planet and the "inner limits" of a person (A. Pechcei, 379).

The era of informationization and globalization, the era of rapid changes, in which all processes are developing rapidly and at the same time contradictory, has begun. The global change of the world order, the systemic nature of the changes taking place on the planet forces us to think about the general laws of history, the deep logic of the change of times.

Fundamental changes in worldview, social psychology and mentality seem to be no less than changes in the material, eventful life of society, because the first one is the main factor of social revolutions that cause huge changes in the economic and political position of the world. The development of information technologies and communication capabilities, the entire powerful arsenal of civilization, significantly weakened the role of geographical spaces and the restrictions imposed by them in the 20th century. Other perspectives of global development have been formed than before, and the configuration of civilizational contradictions has undergone certain metamorphoses.

The new quality of the world - its globalization - was also manifested today when almost the entire planet is covered by a single type of economic practice. New, transnational movement actors have also emerged, loosely linked to the nation-states that host their activities in their territories. Accordingly, the principles of building international management systems and the tasks facing them have changed.

At the same time, global governance does not mean unifying the social and economic life of our planet. The management phenomenon creates a management mindset. However, according to many researchers, in the course of their evolution, management theory and practice has reached a point where it is necessary to combine various models of the research topic.

It has become necessary to create a management meta-theory based on a holistic concept that combines sociology, economics, psychology, cultural studies, philosophy and management methods and ideas. The main problem that prevents management from becoming a science is the individual. His behavior is unpredictable, because it is determined by various factors and circumstances - values, needs, worldview, attitude, level of voluntary actions, that is, what cannot be foreseen and taken into account.

Modern social management still does not meet the requirements of the times. It is necessary to renew it, make fundamental changes that will allow us to affect the main cause of the crisis of general management - the worsening of the contradiction between the subject and the object of management. The most important condition for solving these problems is the increasing role of cultural and socio-psychological factors. Reasonable principles, knowledge, modern concepts, and high-tech tools are of special importance in management culture.

It can be seen that knowledge of the nature of the processes taking place in a special management movement, first of all, begins with the promotion of new ideas that describe the content of management, the level of management thinking. There is no effective management without the ability to set innovative goals and objectives, and then find adequate ways to address them. Management ideas play an equally important role.

Today, leaders understand the principles of revealing the creative potential of each employee, the culture and psychology of human communication, and give priority to the study of human behavior in social organizations and society. In a word, knowing and understanding a person, the forms of his behavior in a social organization is the most important element of management culture and the essence of the management revolution that the world is experiencing.

Individuals working as carriers of knowledge and intelligence in modern management systems are organized and interactive, besides, they constantly improve their intellectual capabilities, therefore intelligence as the basis of personality is neglected from the point of view of science or from the point of view of the practice of personal organization. It is illegal to leave.

Carriers of new management and organizational culture are both the whole society and its separate social groups, first of all educated layers and finally individuals. Today, the idea of forming a modern political and management elite, which can influence public life with a proactive approach, relying on professional knowledge, creative imagination, unconventional perception and innovation, is particularly promising.

The general requirements, standards and principles of social and individual culture are violated in a unique way by its special social importance, moral and legal imperatives, strict regulation of life, special conditions and methods of performing professional duties through the characteristics that determine the essence of the modern leader's activity.

An important theoretical condition for assessing the overall development of the management culture problem of a leader and solving it is the numerous works of domestic and foreign scientists devoted to the philosophical consideration of culture as a form of social consciousness, a social phenomenon, and a spiritual and practical attitude.

The analysis of trends in the development of education allows us to focus on the need to develop the management culture of a manager and the possibility of considering its formation as the goal and result of education. Let us make it clear that the formation of the concept of "management culture of a leader" that we are developing depends on the preferred interpretations of management.

In studying the phenomena of educational activity, the main attention is paid to correcting the content of relevant concepts. Each science reflects its research subject in concepts and categories, without which it is impossible to construct a theory that explains knowable reality. In education, there should be not a collection of different concepts, but a system of their conceptual interrelation, reflected in terminology.

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